

THE EFFECT OF COMPENSATION AND WORKLOAD ON TURNOVER INTENTION WITH JOB SATISFACTION AS INTERVENING VARIABLE ON PT. INTIKOM BERLIAN MUSTIKA (INTIKOM)

WIDYAWATI

Master of Management, Mercu Buana University, Indonesia. Correspondent Email: soemitro.widya@gmail.com

MASYDZULHAK DJAMIL MZ

Professors of Faculty of Business & Management, Mercu Buana University, Indonesia.
Email: masydk@gmail.com, <https://orcid.org/0000-00002-6769-3273>

Abstract:

The purpose of this study was to analyze how the effect of compensation and workload on turnover intention with job satisfaction as intervening variable on turnover intention at PT. Intikom (Intikom Berlian Mustika). Comparative causal research design (quantitative research type) is used by the author in this study. Non-Probability Sampling technique was used for sampling as many as 150 people from a total population of 420 people, which is the total employees of PT. Intikom, while Partial Least Square (PLS) which is a covariance-based SEM is used as an analysis tool. The research results prove that (1) compensation affects Turnover Intention negative and significant (2) Workload affects Turnover Intention positive and significant, (3) Compensation affects job satisfaction positive and significant. (4) Workload has a negative and significant effect on job satisfaction (5) Turnover intention is negative and significant influenced by job satisfaction (6) Turnover intention is positive and significant influenced by compensation through job satisfaction. (7) Workload through Job Satisfaction effect on Turnover Intention positive and significant. Suggestion and input to PT. Intikom pays more and more attention to salary policies that correspond to the workload and skills of its employees.

Keyword: Compensation, Workload, Job Satisfaction, and Turnover Intention.

PRELIMINARY

Human Resources (HR) is a very important resource for the success and existence of a company to achieve the goals that have been set in the competitive business world. Because it is important to manage the company's human resources and maintain employee morale so that it always has a positive impact on the development of the company. According to (Widayati & Yunia, 2016) companies must pay special attention to employees, namely treating them fairly in return for their contributions to the company. Therefore, the company can manage and care for human resources as well as possible.

Existing employee management can reduce problems that often arise in companies, namely turnover intentions. The high turnover rate makes the organization not effective enough because the company loses experienced employees and has to re-practice new employees (Saklit, 2017). According to Gillies (1989), staff turnover is considered high if it exceeds 10% per year and typical if it falls between 5 and 10% per year.

The phenomenon that occurs in this study is the high level of turnover intention at PT. Intikom. PT Intikom is a company engaged in the field of Information Technology (IT) with its address at Jalan Kuningan Barat 2 No.11, South Jakarta. The ideal condition of Human Resources is certainly highly expected to occur at PT. Intikom. However, the reality is that there are many problems related to human resources.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES

Human Resources Management.

Human Resource Management is an activity of planning, procurement, development, maintenance, etc. using human resources to achieve the goals of each individual and organization. This definition is in line with Sutrisno, (2017), while Larasati, (2018) emphasizes more on the process aspect, and Armstrong, (2014) more on an integrated and coherent strategy. According to Mathis and Jackson (2017), human resource management is a formal system developed in an organization related to the management of human talent to achieve organizational goals

Turnover Intention

Turnover intention is a voluntary or involuntary attitude that exists in employees who have the desire or act of leaving the organization either temporarily or moving to find another better job, this definition is in line with that conveyed by Tjahjono, (2017), Chen et al., (2018), and Fitriani and Yusiana (2020).

Compensation

Compensation is everything that employees receive is given by the company as a reward for devoting energy and thoughts to the progress of the company, this definition is in accordance with that stated by Hasibuan (2016), Rivai (2017), Siddiqi and Tangem (2018)

Workload

According to Authar (2019), workload is a process used by someone to finish a task or a series of positions carried out under normal circumstances in a specific amount of time. It is this workload that distinguishes a worker's skills from the demands of the job, causing boredom. On the other hand, excessive fatigue occurs when the skills of the worker do not match the demands of the job. This definition is in line with that conveyed by Firdaus (2017) and Sutikno (2020)

Job Satisfaction

Mahardika & Wibawa (2019) explained that job satisfaction is an important determining factor that encourages people to carry out their work and duties with full responsibility and dedication. According to Nabawi (2020) the happiness of activities is related to feelings and actions towards the profession itself, income, advertising and learning opportunities, supervision, activity partners, activity weights, and others. Based on the explanation above, we can conclude that the level of job satisfaction is the attitude of employees in responding and responding

emotionally to their work. This can be reflected in the behavior of employees when evaluating whether it is good or bad and whether they are happy with their work

Based on the description above, the research hypothesis can be formulated as follows:

- H1: Compensation has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention
- H2: Workload has a positive and significant effect on turnover intention
- H3: Compensation has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction.
- H4: Workload has a negative and significant effect on job satisfaction
- H5: Job Satisfaction has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention
- H6: Compensation through job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on turnover intention
- H7: Workload has a positive and significant influence on Turnover Intention through Job Satisfaction

Figure 1: Framework Study

METHODOLOGY

Comparative causal design is included in the type of quantitative research, used to explain the causal relationship between variables through hypothesis testing. According to Sugiyono (2017) Quantitative study is a method based a positivist philosophy that studies certain populations and or samples, research tools used for data collection, and the analysis has quantitative or statistical properties to test the given hypothesis, used to analyze data.

In this study the population is employees at PT. Intikom a total of 420 employees, with the sample used in this study only employees who are permanent employees of PT. Intikom totaling 150 employees. For sampling using Non-Probability Sampling, which is a technique where all members or members of the population have unequal possibilities or opportunities to be selected as samples (Sugiyono, 2017).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data Quality Test Results

Evaluation of Measurement (outer) Model

Inter Value Model Research Model Constructs and Dimensions use SmartPLS 3.0

Test Results Discriminant Validity

Another way to check discriminant validity is to examine the square root of the average variance extracted (AVE) value for each configuration and the relationship between the configurations in the model and other configurations. The value of discriminant validity is said to be good

Table 1: Test Results Discriminant Validity (Cross loadings)

	Compensation	Workload _	Job Satisfaction	Turnover Intention
K1	0.566	0.359	0.311	0.542
K2	0.816	0.264	0.499	0.489
K3	0.793	0.753	0.645	0.662
K4	0.583	0.189	0.429	0.148
BK1	0.511	0.765	0.511	0.184
BK2	0.409	0.804	0.452	0.725
BK3	0.588	0.598	0.418	0.317
BK4	0.510	0.795	0.628	0.711
BK5	0.581	0.736	0.541	0.327
BK6	0.441	0.883	0.591	0.550
BK7	0.547	0.831	0.284	0.763
BK8	0.289	0.750	0.248	0.571
KK1	0.236	0.508	0.699	0.628
KK2	0.592	0.562	0.948	0.541
KK3	0.299	0.528	0.572	0.331
KK4	0.509	0.194	0.604	0.284
KK5	0.522	0.586	0.634	0.248
KK6	0.489	0.692	0.927	0.817
KK7	0.398	0.286	0.739	0.494
KK8	0.791	0.335	0.889	0.573
KK9	0.118	0.384	0.587	0.522
KK10	0.588	0.559	0.788	0.318
KK11	0.428	0.465	0.792	0.425
T1	0.179	0.687	0.364	0.593
T2	0.272	0.69	0.284	0.853
T3	0.178	0.568	0.439	0.659
T4	0.118	0.287	0.645	0.851
T5	0.509	0.458	0.425	0.772
T6	0.633	0.611	0.816	0.873

Source: Results and processing SmartPLS 3.0

Table 2: AVE Test Results

Variable	AVE
Compensation	0.849
Workload	0.811
Job Satisfaction	0.867
Turnover Intention	0.792

Source: Results and processing SmartPLS 3.0

Table 3: Test Results Discriminant Validity (Fornell Lacker Criterion)

	Compensation	Workload_	Job Satisfaction	Turnover Intention
Compensation	0.869			
Workload _	0.527	0.796		
Job Satisfaction	0.455	0.366	0.879	
Turnover Intention	0.579	0.697	0.718	0.896

Source: Results and processing SmartPLS 3.0

Test Results Composite Reliability & Cronbach's Alpha

Table 4: Test Results Composite Reliability & Cronbach's Alpha

Variable	Composite Reliability	Cornbach's Alpha	Information
Compensation	0.886	0.876	Reliable
Workload	0.817	0.805	Reliable
Job Satisfaction	0.792	0.793	Reliable
Turnover Intention	0.769	0.823	Reliable

Source: Results and processing SmartPLS 3.0

Hypothesis Testing (Inner Model) or Structural Model Testing

Testing Results R-square value

Table 5: Endogenous Variables (R value ²)

Endogenous Variables	R-square
Job Satisfaction	0.897
Turnover Intention	0.848

Source: Results and processing SmartPLS 3.0

Goodness of Fit Model Testing Results

Relevance prediction value (Q2) is used to test the structural Goodness of Fit Model on the inner model. $Q2 > 0$ indicates the model has predictive relevance. The R-squared value for each endogenous variable can be seen in the following calculation, where the value related to the prediction is given by Equation:

$$Q^2 = 1 - (1 - R1) (1 - R_p)$$

$$Q^2 = 1 - (1 - 0,897)(1 - 0,848)$$

$$Q^2 = 1 - (0,103)(0,152)$$

$$Q^2 = 0,984$$

Hypothesis Testing Results (Estimated Path Coefficient)

Table 6: Hypotesis Testing Results

	Original Sample	Standard Deviation	T Statistics	P Values	Information
Compensation > Turnover Intention	-0.474	0.208	2,378	0.001	Negative - Significant
Workload > Turnover Intention	0.426	0.189	3,947	0.004	Positive - Significant
Compensation > Job Satisfaction	0.473	0.325	2,264	0.001	Positive - Significant
Workload > Job Satisfaction	-0.294	0.265	2,771	0.000	Negative - Significant
Job Satisfaction > Turnover Intention	-0.385	0.309	2,533	0.004	Negative - Significant

Source: Results and processing SmartPLS 3.0

Coefficient model track t statistics structural research model

Table 7: Indirect Effect Value

	Original Sample	Standard Deviation	T Statistics	P Values	Information
Influence no direct					
Compensation > Job Satisfaction > Turnover Intention	0.362	0.439	2,189	0.006	Positive - Significant
Workload > Job Satisfaction > Turnover Intention	0.271	0.397	2,607	0.003	Positive - Significant

Source: Results and processing SmartPLS 3.0

Results Discussion

- 1) The Impact of Compensation on Intention to Turnover Based on the study's hypothesis test, the original sample value was -0.474, the T-statistic value was 2.378, and the P value was 0.001. The original sample value displays a negative score, the T-statistic value is more than the T-table value, 1.96, and the P Values value displays an insufficient value of 0.05. This result suggests that compensation has a negative and significant impact on turnover intention. As confirmed by Dini and Purba's (2020) claim that pay has a positive and large impact on turnover intention, other research also demonstrate that there is a considerable negative association between compensation and turnover intention.
- 2) Workload Impacts Turnover Intention Based on the study's hypothesis test, the original sample value was 0.426, the T-statistic value was 3.947, and the P value was 0.004. The original sample value shows a positive score, the T-statistic value is more than the T-table value is 1.96, and the P Values reveals an insufficient value of 0.05. This result demonstrates that Workload has a positive and significant effect on Turnover Intention. According to Ocha Medika Aditya, Basthoumi Muslih, and Restin Meilina (2021), workload has a favorable and significant impact on turnover intention. Other research has also shown a significant positive association between workload and turnover intention.
- 3) Compensation's impact on job satisfaction According to this study's hypothesis testing, the original sample value of 0.473, the T-statistic value of 2.264, and the P-value of 0.001 were obtained. The original sample value indicates a positive score, the T-statistic value is more than the T-table value is 1.96, and the P Values value indicates that it is insufficient to reach 0.05, indicating that remuneration has a positive and substantial impact on job satisfaction. The claim made by Emma Rukmini and Susi Hendriani (2017) that remuneration has a positive and considerable impact on job happiness is confirmed by other studies that demonstrates the existence of a significant positive association between pay and job satisfaction.
- 4) Workload's Impact on Job Satisfaction Based on the results of this study's hypothesis testing, the original sample value of -0.294, the T-statistic value of 2.771, and the P value of 0.000. The original sample value displays a negative score, the T-statistic value is more than the T-table value, 1.96, and the P Values value displays an insufficient value of 0.05. This result suggests that the workload has a negative and substantial impact on job satisfaction. This research is in line with the research results of Mahendrawan & Ayu (2015), and Yo & Ida (2015) where job satisfaction has a negative and significant impact on workload.
- 5) Job satisfaction has an influence on turnover intention. From the calculation results, the number T-statistic = 2.553 > 1, 96 and the P value was. 0, 004 < 0, 05 so H₅ is accepted, the coefficient value is -0.385, thus Turnover Intention has a negative and significant effect on Job Satisfaction of PT. Intikom. This result is in line with the results of Pristianahadi and Nawangsari (2019) where job satisfaction has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention

- 6) Compensation has an effect on Turnover Intention through Job Satisfaction. From the research results obtained T-statistics = 2.189 which is > 1.96 , and P Values of 0.006 which is < 0.05 , so H_6 is accepted, with a coefficient value of 0.362, which means that compensation has an influence on Turnover Intention through Job Satisfaction of PT employees. Intikom positively and significantly. In line with research from Muhamad Sutikno (2020) that the level of employee turnover intention is influenced by compensation through employee satisfaction.
- 7) Workload affects Turnover Intention through Job Satisfaction. From this study it was found that the T-statistic = 2.607 is greater than 1.96, and P Values = 0.003 which is < 0.05 , it can be stated that H_7 is accepted. Coefficient value of 0.271 this result proves that workload through job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on turnover intention. This result is in line with Muhamad Sutikno (2020) whose research results state that workload through employee satisfaction effectively builds turnover intention.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

Based on research conducted at PT. Intikom, it can be concluded as follows:

- 1) Turnover Intention at PT. Intikom is negative and significant affected by Compensation. This means that if the compensation in a company is bad, it will lead to a higher sense of wanting to leave the company.
- 2) Workload has a positive and significant impact on Turnover Intention at PT. Intikom, This means that if the workload in a company increases or is not appropriate, it will lead to an increasing desire to leave the company.
- 3) Compensation has an effect on Job Satisfaction at PT. Intikom positively and significantly. This means that the right compensation will increase the level of job satisfaction that will be felt by employees. Compensation metrics such as pay, incentives, insurance, and retirement plans make employees feel better, more engaged, and happier.
- 4) At PT. Intikom, the workload has a negative and considerable impact on job satisfaction. Therefore, a heavy workload may make workers less satisfied with their jobs. Employee comfort can be lowered by workload indications, such as whether the desired aim is reached, working circumstances, use of work time, and work standards that are inappropriate, which can lead to employee dissatisfaction.
- 5) Turnover intention at PT. Intikom is negative and significant affected by Job Satisfaction. This means that high job satisfaction can reduce the intention to change jobs. Job satisfaction indicators including job satisfaction, income/salary, promotion, supervision, coaching, and co-workers can reduce employees' intention to move.
- 6) Compensation through Job Satisfaction has an effect on Indefinite Turnover at PT. Intikom positive and significant. Compensation indicators such as salary, incentives, insurance and

pension plans will help employees feel comfortable, resulting in satisfaction, and reduce the employee's desire to leave the company.

- 7) Through job satisfaction, workload has a favorable and significant impact on variable turnover at PT. Intikom. Workload indicators, such as goals to be attained, working circumstances, how working time is used, and unsuitable work standards, have an effect on how satisfied employees are at their jobs. Employees will therefore be motivated to look for a better job since they are dissatisfied with their existing position.

Suggestion

Based on the conclusions above, several suggestions as suggestions can be made for PT. Intikom and for future researchers:

Suggestions for Companies

- 1) Management pays more attention to the salary received every employee behaves fairly, according to the smallest mean on the compensation variable of 3.87 in statement I given a salary that is in accordance with needs.
- 2) Where management pays more attention to the workload received by each employee so that employees can work more effectively and do not feel stressed at work and must comply with procedures, according to the smallest mean on the workload variable 3, 5 0 in the statement Employees feel the workload is not according to job standards.
- 3) The management pays more attention to the frequency in employee side promotions so that employees feel valued at work and there is a level that can be reached by the employee group, according to the smallest mean on the Job Satisfaction variable of 3.54 in the statement the frequency of time promotion employees feel is correct.
- 4) Where management should pay more attention to work weight so as not to cause work stress for employees at work, according to the smallest mean on the Turnover Intention variable of 3.50 in the statement of experiencing work stress.

Suggestions for Further Researcher

For similar aspects, this thesis can be used as a reference, but the contents still need to be reconsidered because it is very possible that some statements are incomplete or not suitable. In addition, other researchers can develop other variables and indicators.

REFERENCE

- Agustine, TD, & Nawangsari, LC (2020). The Effect of Compensation and Work Loads towards Intension of Turnover with Job Satisfaction as a Variable Mediation in Clinic Employees of PT Nayaka Era Husada Branch of Bekasi. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*, 5(7), 1304-1312.
- Authar, RA (2019). Analysis Effect of Workload and Commitment Organization against Employee Performance through Turnover Intention as Intervening Variables. *Business Management Analysis Journal*, 2(2), 79-94.
- Dessler, G. (2013). *Human Resource Management*. Jakarta: Four Salemba.

- Djamil, Masydzulhak, Sutawijaya, AH, & Irawan, S. (2018). The Influence of Climate Organization and Job Satisfaction for Turnover Intention through Work Stress of Employees Pt. American President Line Logistics (Distribution Center Cakung). *International Journal of Managerial Studies and Research*, 6 (1), 42-48.
- Fitriani, LK, & Yusiana, N. (2020). Analysis Influence Compensation and Workload to Satisfaction Employment and Turnover Intention of Core Employees of Food, Kuningan. *Indonesian Journal of Strategic Management*, 3 (2), 1-15.
- Gillies, D.A. (1989). *Management Nursing: An Approach system*, Edition second. Translation Illinois: WB Saunders Company.
- Hadi, NP, & Djamil, M. (2019). Influence Leadership, Compensation, and Workload on Employee Turnover (Study Case: PT. Xyz – Jakarta). *Indicator*, 5 (2), 353528.
- Hasibuan, Malay SP, (2017). *Management Source Power Human*. Edition Revision. Jakarta: Earth characters.
- Koesumowidjojo, S., (2017). *Practical Guide to Preparing Analysis, Workload*. Jakarta: Achieve the Hope of Success.
- Larasati, Sri. (2018). *Management Source Power Human*. Yogyakarta: Depublish
- Luthans, Fred. (2011). *Organizational Behavior: An Evidence-Based Approach*. New York: McGraw-Hill
- Mahardika, I, N, B, P., & Wibawa, I, M, A. (2019). Influence culture organization satisfaction work and commitment organizational on organizational citizenship behavior in employees. *E- Journal Management*, 8 (1)
- Mangkunegara, AA Anwar Prabu. (2016). *Management Source Power Human Company*, PT. Teenager Rosdakarya, Bandung
- Mobley, WH (2011). *Employee Turnover: Cause, Effect and Control (Translation)*. Jakarta: PT Pustaka Binaman Pressindo.
- Mondy, RW, and Martocchio, JJ (2016), *Human Resource Management*, ed. 14, Harlow: Pearson Education.
- Nabawi, R. (2019). Influence Environment Work, Satisfaction Work and Workload against Employee Performance. *Maneggio: Journal Scientific Masters in Management*, 2(2), 170–183. <https://doi.org/10.30596/maneggio.v2i2.3667>
- Nurdiansyah, D., Parwoto, P., & Saluy, AB (2021). The Influence of Leadership, Motivation and Work Stress on Turnover Intention of PT. BCA Finance Karawang Branch. *European Journal of Business and Management Research*, 6 (4), 322-326
- Rivai, V. (2016). *Management Source Power Man for Company: from Theory to practice*. Jakarta: King of Grafindo Persada.
- Robbins, S., & Judge, T. (2016). *Behavior Organization*. Edition 12. Jakarta: Salemba four.
- Sugiyono. (2016). *Management Research Methods . Fifth Edition*, Alfabeta. Bandung.
- Sunyoto, D. (2012). *Theory, Questionnaire, and Data Analysis of Human Resources . Yogyakarta: Center of Academic Publishing Service*.
- Susanto, A., Djamil, M., & Saluy, A. (2021, May). The Influence of Leadership, Performance Appraisal System, Work Motivation on Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance of PT PDSI. In *Proceedings of the 1st MICOSS Mercu Buana International Conference on Social Sciences, MICOSS 2020, September 28-29, 2020, Jakarta, Indonesia*.

- Siddiqi, T., & Tangem, S. (2018). Impact of Work Environment, Compensation and Motivation on the Performance of Employees in the Insurance Companies of Bangladesh. *South East Asia Journal of Contemporary Business, Economics and Law*, 15(5), 153-162.
- Sutikno, M. (2020). Effect of Workload and Compensation against Turnover Intention with Satisfaction Work as Intervening Variables (Study on Employees of PT. Delta Dunia Sandang Textiles. *Conference Scientific Student Unissula (Kimu)* 3, 450 - 473.
- Sutrisno, E., (2017). *Management Source Power Human*. Kencana, Jakarta Tentama, F., Rahmawati, PA, & Muhopilah, P. (2019). The Effect and Implications of Work Stress and Workload on Job Satisfaction. *International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research*, 8(11), 2498–2502
- Widayati, Chess and Yolanda Yunia. (2016). Influence Compensation and Culture Organization against Turnover Intention. *Journal Management Volume XX No. 03*.